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The Global Institution Index

Decreased by 8.01% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered

The Institution Index is a composite indicator that assesses the quality and effectiveness of a country's institutional framework, encompassing a wide range of elements that contribute to the stability, transparency, and efficiency of public institutions. This index measures how well institutions support economic development, governance, and social well-being by evaluating factors such as government effectiveness, regulatory quality, the rule of law, and the control of corruption. A high score on the Institution Index reflects a solid legal and regulatory environment, where the rule of law is respected, corruption is minimized, and public services are delivered effectively. Such a context fosters business confidence, encourages investment, and supports sustainable economic growth. Conversely, a low score indicates weaknesses in these areas, which can hinder economic performance, reduce investor confidence, and exacerbate social inequalities. The Institution Index also considers the protection of property rights, judicial independence, and the efficiency of government operations, all of which are crucial for maintaining a healthy economic environment. Additionally, the index evaluates the degree of inclusivity and accountability in governance, ensuring that institutions are responsive to the needs of all citizens and capable of adapting to changing conditions. This index is fundamental for policymakers, investors, and international organizations, as it provides a comprehensive overview of a country's institutional health, guiding strategic decisions and investments. By highlighting strengths and areas for improvement, the Institution Index serves as a key tool for enhancing institutional quality, promoting good governance, and ultimately driving economic and social progress. The data is available for the period 2013-2022.

The Institution Index in 2022. The 2022 Innovation Index provides a significant overview of the innovative capacity of countries globally, highlighting notable differences among nations. At the top of the ranking is Singapore, with a score of 95.9, reflecting its strong commitment to building an innovation-friendly ecosystem, supported by targeted government policies, a favorable business environment, and substantial investments in research and development. Switzerland follows with a score of 89.2, consolidating its position as a global leader in innovation, thanks to an excellent educational system, strong institutions, and robust public-private collaboration. Norway and the Netherlands, with scores of 87.1 and 86.9 respectively, demonstrate the importance of stable governance and targeted investments in research and technology to maintain high levels of innovation. Countries like Luxembourg and the United Arab Emirates, with scores of 84.6 and 83.5, are examples of nations that, despite their small size, can compete globally due to innovation-oriented policies and the attraction of international talent. A deeper analysis of the ranking reveals that advanced economies continue to dominate the top positions, thanks to well-developed infrastructure, strong institutions, and a high level of human capital. However, countries like New Zealand (83.3) and Estonia (82.2) show that even smaller nations can excel in innovation if supported by effective policies and a constant commitment to technological modernization. The United States, with a score of 80.9, remains a key player in global innovation, despite a slight decline compared to previous

years. This can be attributed to internal challenges such as growing inequality and political fragmentation, which can affect the country's ability to maintain its competitive edge. In Europe, countries like Germany (76.5), France (77), and Sweden (76.5) continue to be leaders in innovation, thanks to a strong industrial tradition, investments in research and development, and favorable public policies. However, their relatively lower scores compared to other advanced economies suggest that they may need to address challenges related to bureaucracy and the need to further modernize their technological infrastructure. The United Kingdom, with a score of 74.5, remains a significant force in innovation but shows signs of stagnation, likely influenced by the economic uncertainties related to Brexit. Asia presents a variety of results, with Singapore and Hong Kong standing out as global innovation hubs, thanks to a combination of proactive policies, advanced infrastructure, and strong connections to global markets. South Korea, with a score of 70.5, is an example of how sustained investments in technology and education can lead to a high level of innovation, although there are signs that further diversification of its approach may be necessary to maintain growth. China, with a score of 64.8, continues to emerge as a global innovation power, although its relatively lower position compared to Western countries indicates that it still has some way to go to close the gap in terms of the quality and sustainability of innovation. Among emerging countries, Mauritius (74.7) and Brunei (74.5) are interesting examples of how small economies can leverage targeted strategies to significantly improve their innovative capacities. India, with a score of 60.1, shows significant progress but still lags behind other BRICS economies, suggesting the need to address structural challenges such as bureaucracy, corruption, and lack of infrastructure. Africa shows a wide variety of scores, with countries like Rwanda (68.8) demonstrating notable progress thanks to innovative policies and effective governance, while other countries, such as Niger (52) and Mauritania (51.6), remain significantly behind, highlighting the difficulties many African nations face in building robust innovation ecosystems. Latin America and the Caribbean present a similar situation, with countries like Chile (66.5) and Uruguay (69.4) showing good results thanks to stable policies and a focus on education and technological innovation, while other nations, like Argentina (47.6) and Brazil (46.7), struggle to keep pace, often due to economic and political instability that hampers innovation development. Mexico, with a score of 48.2, although one of the largest economies in the region, shows a significant margin for improvement, facing challenges related to security, corruption, and the need to modernize its technological infrastructure. Looking at the countries at the bottom of the ranking, such as Yemen (17.5), Iran (31.1), and Zimbabwe (33.3), it becomes clear how conflicts, political instability, and economic sanctions can have a devastating impact on the ability to innovate. These countries face severe deficiencies in infrastructure, human capital, and governance, making it extremely difficult to create an environment conducive to innovation. In such cases, international assistance and substantial internal reforms are necessary to initiate a recovery and improvement path. An interesting aspect that emerges from the analysis of these data is the correlation between the level of economic development and the position in the Innovation Index. Countries with advanced and well-established economies tend to achieve higher scores, suggesting that strong human capital, stable institutions, and advanced infrastructure are key factors for success in innovation. However, there are significant exceptions, such as Mauritius and Rwanda, which demonstrate that even emerging economies can achieve high levels of innovation if supported by effective government policies and a clear strategic vision. In conclusion, the 2022 Innovation Index highlights a significant disparity in innovative capacity among different countries, reflecting not only differences in the level of economic development but also the effectiveness of public policies, the quality of institutions, and the availability of human and technological resources. While some nations continue to consolidate their position as leaders in innovation, others face significant challenges in improving their innovation ecosystems. For countries ranked lower in the index, the path to innovation will require not only investments in research and development but also structural reforms, improvements in governance,

and a constant commitment to building an environment conducive to economic growth and technological progress.

The Institution Index between 2013 and 2022. The data on the Institution Index between 2013 and 2022 highlights significant variations in different countries, both in terms of improvements and deteriorations. A detailed analysis of the data shows that some nations have made remarkable progress, while others have experienced substantial declines, reflecting a variety of economic, political, and social factors. Among the countries with the most significant improvements, Indonesia stands out, having seen an increase of 17.9 points, equivalent to an improvement of 48.12%. This result suggests a significant strengthening of institutions, likely due to structural reforms and increasing political and economic stability. China and Vietnam have also shown substantial progress, with increases of 16.5 points (34.16%) and 14 points (30.04%), respectively. These increases indicate the profound transformations these countries have undergone in recent years, focusing on modernizing institutions and integrating into the global economy. Countries such as Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan, with increases of 11.9 and 10.2 points respectively, also show an improvement in institutional quality, often associated with efforts to improve governance and reduce corruption. In Africa, nations like Rwanda and Côte d'Ivoire have shown significant progress, with improvements of 15.82% and 18.44%, respectively, demonstrating how targeted investments and government reforms can lead to institutional strengthening even in contexts with limited resources. At the same time, some countries with already strong institutions have continued to improve, albeit at a slower pace. The United Arab Emirates, Singapore, and Switzerland have recorded smaller but significant increases of 10.45%, 4.01%, and 2.18%, respectively, further consolidating their position as global leaders in institutional quality. On the other hand, the situation is very different for countries that have registered a decline in the Institution Index. Among these, Yemen has experienced the worst drop, with a decrease of 19.8 points, equivalent to a decline of 53.08%. This drastic deterioration is undoubtedly linked to the prolonged conflict, political destabilization, and humanitarian crisis that have devastated the country in recent years. Countries such as Belarus and Mozambique have also recorded significant reductions in their scores, with declines of 36.11% and 35.01%, respectively, reflecting increasing political repression and economic instability. In Europe, nations like Slovakia, Poland, and Croatia have seen worrying decreases, with drops of 28.29%, 24.33%, and 23.88%, respectively. These countries, once seen as models of democratic transition and post-communist economic development, are now facing challenges related to the deterioration of the rule of law, increasing corruption, and growing political instability. Even traditionally stable countries such as Finland, Denmark, and Ireland have experienced significant reductions in their Institution Index scores, with declines of 13.43%, 13.12%, and 13.82%, respectively. These data indicate that even in advanced economies, challenges related to governance, transparency, and trust in institutions can emerge. Among Western nations, the United States has recorded a significant drop of 5.1 points, equivalent to a 5.93% decline. This decline can be attributed to various factors, including political polarization, governance crises, and growing inequalities that have characterized the past decade. Countries like the United Kingdom, which saw a 15.72% decline, and Germany, with a 7.27% drop, also show signs of institutional stress, likely linked to political uncertainties and the increasing complexity of economic and social challenges. In Asia, Japan has seen a decline of 7.7 points (9.22%), indicating that even advanced East Asian economies are not immune to institutional difficulties, possibly related to economic stagnation and demographic issues. South Korea, with a decline of 7.24%, reflects similar tensions, despite its impressive technological and industrial progress. In summary, the data from the Institution Index between 2013 and 2022 shows a wide range of

experiences across different countries, with some making significant progress in improving the quality of their institutions, while others have experienced substantial deterioration. The most evident improvements have occurred in developing countries that have invested in structural reforms and governance strengthening, while the most severe declines have been observed in countries affected by conflicts, political instability, and democratic regression. However, many advanced economies have also experienced a decline in institutional quality, suggesting that governance and trust in institutions are global challenges that require constant attention and policy adjustments. These results underscore the importance of strong institutions for economic and social progress and show how political, economic, and social changes can have a profound and lasting impact on the quality of governance.

Economic Policies to Increase the Value of the Institution Index. Increasing the value of the Institution Index requires an integrated economic approach that encompasses a range of policies aimed at strengthening institutions, promoting transparency, enhancing governance efficiency, and combating corruption. One of the fundamental policies for improving the value of the Institution Index is investing in the administrative capacity of public institutions. This means enhancing the training and professionalization of the public workforce, ensuring that public employees are adequately qualified and motivated to operate with integrity and competence. The creation of continuous training programs and the development of a meritocratic culture within public administrations can contribute to improving government effectiveness and the quality of services offered to citizens. At the same time, it is essential to promote transparency at all levels of government. This can be achieved through the implementation of performance monitoring and evaluation systems, which hold the government and institutions accountable to citizens. The digitalization of public services plays a crucial role in this context, allowing for greater accessibility and transparency in government operations. Through digital platforms, citizens can have direct access to government information, participate in decision-making processes, and report inefficiencies or abuses. The use of digital technologies for transparency and participation not only increases citizens' trust in institutions but also reduces opportunities for corruption. Combating corruption is indeed another fundamental pillar for increasing the Institution Index. Corruption erodes trust in institutions and hinders economic development, so it is essential to adopt strict measures to prevent and sanction it. Governments can implement stricter anti-corruption regulations, establish independent oversight bodies, and ensure that laws are enforced impartially. It is also important to promote a culture of public ethics, encouraging transparency and integrity in all sectors of society. Independent media and civil society must be involved as strategic partners in the fight against corruption, playing a role in monitoring and raising awareness. Justice is another critical area to focus on to improve the Institution Index. An independent, efficient, and accessible judiciary is essential to ensure the rule of law, which is the foundation of any healthy economy. Reforming the judiciary to make it faster and less burdensome, investing in judicial infrastructure, and training judges can contribute to improving the quality of institutions. An effective judiciary deters illegal practices and ensures that contracts are respected, which is essential for a favorable business environment. Additionally, the adoption of economic policies aimed at improving the regulatory environment can significantly increase the value of the Institution Index. Clear, consistent, and stable regulations reduce uncertainty for businesses and encourage both local and foreign investments. Governments must work to simplify regulations, eliminate outdated laws, and make administrative processes more streamlined and predictable. This reduces the risk of discretion by public officials, which is often fertile ground for corruption. An efficient regulatory environment promotes competitiveness and fosters innovation, key elements for sustainable economic development.

Administrative decentralization can also play an important role in strengthening institutions. Delegating more powers to local and regional administrations can bring political decisions closer to citizens, making the government more accountable and responsive to local needs. However, decentralization must be accompanied by a clear definition of responsibilities and adequate financial and human resources to avoid inefficiencies and inequalities between different areas of the country. Proper management of public resources is crucial to ensure the sustainability of institutional policies. Governments must adopt rigorous financial management practices, including long-term planning, public expenditure control, and the fight against tax evasion. A fair and transparent fiscal policy is essential to generate the revenue needed to finance public services and infrastructure investments, which in turn strengthen the quality of institutions. Public participation is another crucial element for improving the Institution Index. Involving citizens in the decision-making process, through public consultations and other direct participation tools, can enhance the legitimacy of political decisions and strengthen trust in institutions. Active citizen participation helps ensure that policies reflect the real needs of the population and are therefore more effective. It is also important to promote inclusivity in public policies, ensuring that all social groups, including the most vulnerable, have a say and can benefit from government decisions. In this context, education plays a fundamental role. Investing in civic education and training citizens about their rights and duties is essential to build a more aware and engaged society. An informed populace is more likely to actively participate in public life and hold their representatives accountable, thus contributing to the improvement of institutions. Another critical area is strengthening the rule of law, which requires not only an efficient judiciary but also respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. Protecting property rights, ensuring freedom of expression, and promoting equality before the law are indispensable elements for creating a stable and predictable institutional environment that attracts investments and stimulates economic growth. Finally, international economic integration can help improve the Institution Index. Active participation in global markets and cooperation with international organizations can lead to greater adoption of best practices and international standards in national policies. Openness to trade and foreign investment can also incentivize governments to improve institutions to attract and retain foreign capital, which is often sensitive to the quality of the institutional environment. In summary, to increase the value of the Institution Index, it is necessary to adopt a coherent set of economic policies that promote transparency, efficiency, legality, and participation. Only through consistent and integrated efforts can strong institutions be built, capable of sustaining long-term economic and social development while ensuring the trust of citizens and investors.

Conclusions. On average, the value of the Institution Index decreased between 2013 and 2022 by an amount equal to -8.01% for the countries considered. There are countries where the value of the Institution Index has grown significantly between 2013 and 2023, namely Indonesia with +48.12%, Zimbabwe with +37.60%, China with +34.16%, Vietnam with +30.04%, and Uzbekistan with +26.21%. However, there are also countries where the value of the Institution Index has decreased, such as the Slovak Republic with -28.29%, Nicaragua with -28.49%, Mozambique with -35.01%, Belarus with -36.11%, and Yemen with -53.08%.

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Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Singapore	95,9	Jordan	63,5	Philippines	48,7
Switzerland	89,2	Azerbaijan	62,9	Russian Federation	48,7
Norway	87,1	Portugal	62,5	Tajikistan	48,6
Netherlands	86,9	Hungary	62	Tunisia	48,4
Luxembourg	84,6	Namibia	61,7	Mexico	48,2
United Arab Emirates	83,5	Saudi Arabia	60,6	Bosnia and Herzegovina	48,1
New Zealand	83,3	Vietnam	60,6	Guinea	47,8
Austria	82,8	Kazakhstan	60,5	Argentina	47,6
Denmark	82,8	Serbia	60,4	Ukraine	47,4
Finland	82,5	India	60,1	Moldova	47,3

Hong Kong SAR, China	82,5	Armenia	59,7	Algeria	47,2
Estonia	82,2	Jamaica	59,5	Ghana	46,9
United States	80,9	Italy	59	Turkiye	46,8
Canada	80,4	Oman	59	Brazil	46,7
Iceland	80,4	Montenegro	58,3	Lao PDR	46,7
Ireland	79,2	Senegal	58,1	Cameroon	46,5
Australia	77,2	Peru	58	Burkina Faso	46,3
France	77	Uganda	57,5	Burundi	45,3
Germany	76,5	Benin	57,3	El Salvador	45,3
Sweden	76,5	Uzbekistan	57,3	Togo	45
Japan	75,8	Poland	56,3	Bangladesh	44,1
Mauritius	74,7	Trinidad and Tobago	56,2	Ethiopia	44
Brunei Darussalam	74,5	Bulgaria	55,9	Egypt, Arab Rep.	43,9
United Kingdom	74,5	Slovak Republic	55,5	Nigeria	43,5
Qatar	74,1	Greece	55,2	Kyrgyz Republic	43,2
Bahrain	72	Panama	55,2	Mali	43,1
Lithuania	72	Indonesia	55,1	Paraguay	42,7
Malta	71,8	Cote d'Ivoire	54,6	Angola	41,9
Belgium	71,5	Colombia	54,6	Nepal	41,3
Georgia	70,7	Tanzania	54,2	Pakistan	41,2
Korea, Rep.	70,5	Mongolia	54,1	Sri Lanka	40,8
Uruguay	69,4	Romania	54,1	Madagascar	40,8
Malaysia	68,8	Croatia	52,6	Ecuador	39,4
Rwanda	68,8	Thailand	52,5	Guatemala	39,1
Latvia	68,7	Dominican Republic	52	Myanmar	38
Cyprus	67,5	Niger	52	Nicaragua	37,9
Slovenia	67,4	South Africa	51,9	Honduras	37,7
Spain	66,8	Kenya	51,8	Zambia	37,5
Chile	66,5	Mauritania	51,6	Iraq	36,7
Botswana	65	Albania	51,4	Zimbabwe	33,3
Israel	65	Morocco	51,1	Mozambique	32,3
China	64,8	Kuwait	51	Belarus	32,2
Czechia	64,5	Cambodia	50,4	Iran, Islamic Rep.	31,1
Costa Rica	64,3	North Macedonia	50,4	Yemen, Rep.	17,5